

Education of Students with Autism Spectrum Disorder: Utilization of Educational Software According to the Theory of Behaviorism

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Abstract

The present article investigates the role of intervention programs for students with Autism Spectrum Disorder based on Operant Conditioning, through the use of modern computing technologies. Specifically, it investigates the crucial role of educational software based on the theory of Behaviorism in stimulating motivation and interest as well as in enhancing a wide range of cognitive, social, motor, and emotional skills in students with ASD. By highlighting the ways in which behavioral software utilizes the principles of Behaviorism in shaping behavior, the need to expand research in the field of transferring behavioral software to mobile device applications that will enhance motivation and provision of stimuli to students with ASD, is also recommended.

Keywords: Autism Spectrum Disorder, Educational Software, Theory of Behaviorism

Autism Spectrum Disorder

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is defined by impairment and deviant reactions in the areas of reciprocal social transactions, communication, interests and activities, as well as in general behavior (Faras, Al Ateeqi, & Tidmarsh, 2010). Diagnostic criteria of ASD, as recognized by the "Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition - DSM-5" include deficits in social-emotional reciprocity, in non-verbal communication behaviors used in social interaction, in development, maintenance and understanding of relationships, stereotypical or repetitive movements, persistence in ritualistic patterns, extremely limited interests in abnormal intensity or focus and hyper- or hypo-reactivity to sensory stimuli (APA, 2013), while correspondingly several subtypes of ASD are recorded (Grzadzinski, Huerta, & Lord, 2013).

Most researchers agree that ASD is due to organic rather than psychogenic factors. Nevertheless, it is not clear whether these causes are diverse or they converge on one organic factor (Genovese & Butler, 2020). The main features of ASD symptomatology include basic deficits in attention (distraction or avoidance of eye contact), in verbal speech (echolalia, incomprehensible articulation, stereotypical - incoherent speech), in social and emotional expressions (weakness or lack of interest in communication and social interaction), in playing (idiosyncratic use or obsessive attachment to specific toys) and in cognitive functions (cognitive delay or cognitive deficits), while one of the most common features of ASD is the selective focus of attention on specific environmental stimuli (Coulter, 2009; Johnston, 2019).

Theory of Behaviorism and ASD

Regarding treatment of ASD, various scientific findings demonstrate the effectiveness of the use of techniques derived from the theory of Behaviorism and, in particular, from the Operant Conditioning model, a process of gradual shaping of an intended response through the positive or negative reinforcement of individual behaviors that resemble it (Pervin & John 2001). Modification of the frequency of the operant behaviors is determined by the factors of "reinforcement" and "punishment". Positive reinforcement leads to an increase in the frequency of the desired behavior due to its association with a positive stimulus, positive punishment leads to a decrease in the frequency of the behavior due to its association with a negative stimulus, negative punishment causes a decrease in the frequency of the behavior due to the withdrawal of an associated positive stimulus and negative reinforcement causes an increase in the frequency of the behavior due to the withdrawal of an associated negative stimulus (Gena, 2002).

	Addition of Consequence	Removal of Consequence
Increase in frequency of desired behavior	Positive Reinforcement	Negative Reinforcement
Decrease in frequency of desired behavior	Positive Punishment	Negative Punishment

Table 1: Functions of Operant Conditioning

Gradual shaping of behavior or the method of successive approximations, as proposed by Skinner (1976), is one of the most widely used methods of shaping operant behaviors, with an array of scientific evidence of its effectiveness in treating students with ASD (Sundberg & Michael, 2001). The model is defined as teaching successive responses that are gradually closer approximations of the final desired behavior. During the successive stages of the process, responses that are closer to the final behavior are reinforced, while deviant responses are eliminated (Johnson, Kohler, & Ross, 2017). The goal of the whole process is to improve the gradual responses until the final behavior is achieved. In this context, the learning of the intended response is broken down into the three successive steps of mastering an initial, an intermediate, and a final or completed goal (Delprato, & Midgley, 1992).

Figure 1. Stages of Operant Conditioning (Tan, Kasivelloo, & Abdullah, 2022).

Also, the formation of a calm psychological climate with a friendly atmosphere, the constant and continuous motivation of interest and attention, the provision of simple, clear and unambiguous instructions with clear language, gestures and symbols, the provision of measured, prudent assistance, as frequent praise, encouragement and empowerment of students with ASD as possible as a stimulus to active participation in learning processes, the frequent repetition and the necessary evaluation of each correct or incorrect action (Kyriotakis, 1997), are considered to be decisive.

Behaviorism and Educational Software

The learning theories and the teaching approaches on which they are based, are amongst the main criteria for categorizing educational software (Espinoza, Perdomo, & Flores, 2006). One of the first and main theories for the development of educational software was the theory of Behaviorism (Winn, & Snyder, 1996), according to which computers acquired their first educational dimension (Quintana, et al., 2002). The learning effectiveness of software based on the Behavioral learning theory has always been directly related to the learning environment in which it was used and to the level of ability and potential of the students using it (McGowan & Clark, 1985). Nowadays there is an increase in the educational applications of Behaviorism in the use of new learning technologies and digital tools (Gunnars, 2021). By utilizing the principles of Behaviorism, the above software can support flexibility and productivity in displaying and visualizing information and data (Forbes, Höllerer, & Legrady, 2010), while serving multiple educational needs in relation to a variety of curricula, assessment methods, and teaching materials (Weegar & Pacis, 2012).

As a basis for the design of educational software according to the theory of Behaviorism, we can consider direct or indirect feedback, as a response to the learner's choices within the software environment (Cooper, 1993), which ultimately aims at changing a behavior, as a result of the experience of using the software (Deubel, 2003). In this way, the design of educational software focuses on students' response to stimuli, on motivating the intended behavior and on linking stimuli to actions that enhance

learning (Eugenio & Ocampo, 2019). Behavioral software encourages the practice of specific skills of graded and escalating difficulty through direct rewards and clear indications of success or failure (Spyropoulou, et al., 2013).

Figure 2: Example of positive and negative reinforcement in software for students with ASD (Munoz, et al., 2018)

Behavioral software and ASD

The use of assistive technologies and specialized software is crucial to support students with ASD (Wei, 2014), as it can enhance cognitive development and reduce irritability (Guerra & Furtado, 2014). Students with ASD show interest and motivation in using new technologies (Goodwin, 2008) and educational multimedia and computer games (Kee, 2009; da Silva, & Bissaco, 2022), while educational software, in addition to developing cognitive skills, enhances social and communication skills more broadly (Hayes, 2007).

Figure 3: Categorization of computing technologies for ASD (Alves, et al., 2020)

The basic principles of designing computing technologies for students with ASD include the structured and predictable individual or collaborative learning environment, progression, feedback and reward, error management, and a variety of skills related to daily life (Valencia, 2020). In this context, the design of software for students with ASD emphasizes procedural error tolerance, feedback, and visual harmony (Mahmoudi, Badie, & Varnousfaderani, 2015). Software applications developed for students with ASD according to the theory of Behaviorism, can structure a learning environment of educational activities that facilitate the acquisition of targeted social behaviors (Farias, et al., 2013) and support the emotional connection with the software, which enhances frequency of software use (Mintz, 2014). At the same time, behavioral educational software supports learning through play (Ahmad, et al., 2010), and it can be transferred to different platforms, such as computers, mobile devices or even augmented reality devices, maintaining the same cognitive and learning principles across different educational programs (Presti, et al., 2017).

Figure 4: Graphical interface of behavioral software for students with ASD (Ahmad, et al., 2010)

Discussion

The design of effective intervention programs for students with ASD based on Operant Conditioning, is recommended to consider the principles of individualized instruction, taking into account the particular capabilities and deficits, the learning history, the cultural differences and peculiarities, the particular emotional state and the heterogeneous clinical picture of each pupil with ASD. Educational software according to the theory of Behaviorism can play a decisive role in this effort, providing appropriate incentives to students with ASD, maintaining their interest and emotional connection during the learning process and supporting the development of a wide range of skills. The need for further research in the field of transferring behavioral software to applications for new mobile devices, which will be easier to use educationally, more accessible, and will increase motivation to use and provision of stimuli, to shape behavior of students with ASD, is also recommended.

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